

Collaborative governance in thermal tourism development In Algeria, Case study of hammam Grouz (sidi kassem) in oued athmania municipality, mila province

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Abstract

In Algeria, the new major challenge for tourism as a social and economic activity is how tourism stakeholders interact and how this interaction can be beneficial in improving the tourist destination. This research aims to find an effective collaborative governance model that can be applied in thermal tourism development. The research used a qualitative method with a case study approach, Hammam Sidi Kassem in Oued Athmania municipality, and the data were collected through interviews and observations in addition to field trips. The actors listed are government, private sector and local authority. The findings suggest that cooperative governance does not work properly due to the disintegration of cooperative links between the various decision-makers, the relationship between the current actors cannot contribute to improving the status of thermal tourism in the region due to lack of integration, power asymmetry, and divergent interests among the actors. The fragmented nature of the tourism industry, centralization of decisions, multiple stakeholders in thermal.

Key words: thermal Tourism, Collaborative Governance, hammam sidi kassem, government, local authority, Private sector

1 Introduction

Algeria is one of the countries rich in heritage. Its cultural diversity and historical wealth tell a story filled with significant events, from ancient civilizations to the colonial period, including the Phoenicians, Romans, Muslims, and Ottomans (Djaber & Dekoumi, 2022). Thermalism in Algeria is not a recent phenomenon; in fact, the Romans were among the first to harness the waters that sprang from the subsoil, leaving behind historical evidence of their therapeutic benefits. History reveals that the Romans, during their settlement in North Africa, discovered "noria of griffins" (Berkani & Houha, 2017). The local inhabitants regarded thermal practices as a sacred remedy for various ailments, a tradition shaped by the fusion of past civilizations. According to Babilee (1927), the local population used mineral water springs for daily bathing, either by repurposing rudimentary Roman pools or by digging their own basins, alongside setting up tents for temporary stays (Nedjar & Chergui, 2018). A study conducted in 2015 by Algeria's Ministry of Tourism and Handicrafts to assess thermal resources across the country revealed the existence of 282 thermal springs, either natural or drilled. In addition to the 90 existing concessions for hydrothermal water use, and considering the physicochemical properties and therapeutic value of these waters, there are currently around 100 hydrothermal sources suitable for new projects, including 34 traditionally operated mineral baths. Given its significance, thermalism in Algeria is a priority for economic development, thanks to the country's vast untapped thermal potential—particularly in the eastern regions—and the growing public demand for leisure, relaxation, healthcare, fitness, and wellness (Berkani & Houha, 2017).

Among the Algerian provinces with significant water potential is the province of Mila, located in eastern Algeria. Known as "the water province," Mila has a history dating back to the Neolithic era. Over time, it has

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been home to many civilizations, leaving behind numerous historical monuments worth exploring. The region is also rich in diverse landscapes, including mountains, plateaus, and plains. One of Mila's most distinguishing features is its abundant water resources, such as the large Beni Haroun Dam. Additionally, the province has 13 natural thermal springs with therapeutic benefits (Saifi, 2023). Many specialists agree that analyses of Mila's thermal waters indicate strong curative properties. However, most of these springs remain underutilized, operating only in traditional hammams that fail to meet modern hydrotherapy standards (Adel & Bekhouche, 2016). Among the most popular thermal baths in southern Mila is Hammam Sidi Kassem (Hammam Grouz), located in the municipality of Oued Athmania. Established during the Roman era, the site later became home to the Sidi Kassem Zawiya during the Islamic period. After Algeria's independence, it retained its historical and cultural significance, attracting tourists for bathing and leisure while remaining an important part of the region's identity. The current study reveals that thermal tourism potential in Mila is underutilized, with thermal sources not being exploited optimally. Key reasons for this include: Lack of infrastructure and equipment, Poor marketing, insufficient intervention by state and local authorities, most demand comes from the domestic market, driven by affordable services and local traditions. Governance in the thermal tourism sector remains challenging due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders with limited awareness of thermal tourism's potential. Additionally, the sector faces threats and opportunities from political, social, environmental, and technological trends.

2 Material and methods

There is no settled view concerning the parameters of case study research but, broadly speaking, case study research aims to explore and depict a setting with a view to advance understanding of it. In presenting ideas and techniques for case study research (Glynis, 2005) case studies can be especially valuable for research on the governance of tourism as they allow for the careful weighting of the structural pressures and contingent social practices based on specific actors at particular conjunctures. In addition, case studies can expand practical understandings, sharpen critical judgement (Shone et al., 2016). This Researchers select methods of data collection and analysis that will generate material suitable for case studies such as qualitative techniques. (Barandiaran et al., 2019). The research used qualitative method with a case study approach. Data are collected through interviews, documentation study, and observation and literature reviews. The content of the paper is divided into three sections: Firstly, presentation the theoretical foundation of governance in tourism. Secondly, study the potentials and challenges of Thermal Tourism in the in study area (hammam sidi kassem) through a SWOT analysis. Third, it discusses an approach to collaborative governance, in addition to the final conclusions. Hence, this research paper addresses Answer the following questions

- Is collaborative governance a real source that contributes to the development of the tourism sector?
- What are the most important reasons hindering internal changes for the development of thermal tourism in the study area?
- Identify the role of actors in the field of tourism governance?
- Find a collaborative governance model that can be applied in the area for tourism development

3. Literature review

3.1. collaborative governance

Over the past few decades, a new form of governance has emerged to replace adversarial and managerial modes of policy making and implementation. Collaborative governance, as it has come to be known, brings public and private stakeholders together in collective forums with public agencies to engage in consensus-oriented decision making. (Ansell & Gash, 2007) Given that Most contemporary issues are highly complex and diverse and cannot be resolved by a single actor alone. Thus, most communities in the world seek to manage their concerns collectively in order to achieve the goals of sustainable development and solve their conflicts (Tae Byung, 2010). "Collaborative" describes a process through which parties who see different aspects of a problem can constructively explore their differences and seek solutions. "Governance" was first defined in 1992 by the World Bank and referred to as a decision-making process to implement new initiatives and resolve issues (Biancone et al., 2022). Although there is still no exact definition of the term, it has generally come to be accepted that

governance is “a new mode of governing that is distinct from the hierarchical control model, a more cooperative mode where state and non-state actors participate (fernandez et al., 2017).The collaborative governance is also defined as an arrangement that regulates one or more public institutions to directly engage with non-public stakeholders in a formal, consensus- oriented, and deliberative collective decision-making process that aims to create or to implement public policies or to manage public programs or public assets (slamet Santoso & Djumiarti, 2020). The decision-making processes in a collaborative governance approach are shared among public and private stakeholders and are presented as being horizontally related his process, which is found in public participation, occurs with the redistribution of power that enables the inclusion of citizens who have been historically excluded. This redistribution aims at more equitable policy outcomes while also providing residents with greater power over their environments The virtues of collaborative governance have given rise to a number of collaborative planning exercises (Débora et al., 2021) Collaboration is more likely to occur (a) when goals are likely to be achieved, and (b) when the benefits of collaboration are relatively achievable, and (c) when small wins of collaboration accrue quickly. Although intermediate outcomes may show real benefit, the critical process is cyclic, and reiterated outcomes build the momentum of success. “Little victories” encourage subsequent cycles to build trust and commitment (Ridwan et al., 2019)

3.2. Collaborative governance in tourism

Tourism governance is one of the issues that is significantly a concern for scholars in the world who have attention to development policies for tourism planning, this is considered important because researchers have tried to understand how countries can act best to mediate social, economic, political and environmental policy issues related to tourism (Kodir et al., 2020). Where Murphy's book was followed from the late 1980s by a considerable research output concerning participation in tourism policy-making. This includes work by Jamal and Getz (1995) on collaborative policy-making in tourist destinations, Sofield's (2003) discussion of tourism planning and the political and social empowerment of communities, and Garrod's (2003) suggestions for strategies to promote effective community participation in planning for ecotourism (Bramwell, 2010). Where several studies found larger benefits for communities when local stakeholders could participate in the tourism value chain by ‘linking’ their labour, products and services to the sector (Adiyia et al., 2015). Governance in tourism has been defined as a system and process to define strategies and implement them to achieve competitiveness and sustainable development of the tourism destination (Scott, 2015) Tourism governance can be defined as “a measurable practice of governance, which aims to manage tourism effectively at the different levels of governance, through forms of coordination, collaboration and/or cooperation that are effective, transparent and accountable, which will help to achieve the collectively shared objectives shared by stakeholder networks involved in the sector, with a view to developing solutions and opportunities through agreements based on recognition of interdependencies and shared responsibility (Pulido-Fernández & Pulido-Fernández Ignacio, 2019). Governance is a multi-faceted concept and along with its multi-scalar nature in tourism, this helps to explain the plurality of approaches that have been taken in understanding, firstly, the nature of governance in tourism, and, secondly, how to govern the tourism industry effectively (Antonio dos Anjos & Kennell ,2018). Where it can be asserted that the impact of governance on the tourism industry is crucial for two reasons. First, understanding the split between policy design and implementation is of particular importance for the tourism industry where a multi-level and well-established policy framework is ultimately required. Second, a cooperation mechanism among the state, civil society and interest groups which can be enhanced through governance quality helps increase the benefits from the tourism industry (Topcuet et al., 2023)

4. Potentials and challenges of thermal tourism

4.1. Description of the study area

The municipality of Oued athmania is located in the province of Mila in the east. It is bordered to the north by Ibn Ziyad and Sidi Khalifa, to the east by the municipality of Ain Smara in the province of Constantine, to the west by the municipality of Ain El Melouk, to the southeast by the municipality of Oued Segane, and to the southwest by the municipality of Chelghoum El Aid. Naturally, the municipality of Oued athmania belongs to the region of the High Plains of Constantine. It contains the grouz Dam, the second dam in eastern Algeria (Map No 1-2).

4.2 Hammam (grouz) sidi kassem

The Hammam grouz is also called Hammam Sidi Kassem is located one kilometer south of the village of Oued Athmania about a hundred meters from the national road N ° 5 Algiers-Constantine. The hot springs emerge on the right bank of the Oued Rhumel which crosses mountain Grouz and then the city. The water source of Hammam Sidi Kassem is from the grouz Mountains spring, which is located directly above the hammam the Physicochemical properties of the waters is: Temperatures varying from (43°C and 45°C), The pH values indicate acidic waters (6.56 and 6.65), The conductivity is high (2151.36 and 2275.35µmhos/cm), The mineralization is important; it varies from (1426.41 to 1439.87 mg/l), (Mammeri, 2015)

Figure 1. Administrative location of mila province
In eastern Algeria

Source: authors

Figure 2. Administrative location of oued athmania municipality

Source: authors

Figure 3. The source of Hammam Sidi Kassem is in the grouz Mountains.

Source: Mammeri (2015)

The origins of the first establishment of Hammam sidi kassem go back to the Roman period, which occupied the province of Mila in 112 BC. After the Islamic conquest, the corners spread throughout Algeria. The corner is a place of worship and memorization of the Qur'an and a place for visitors. The hammam was named after the founder of the corner, Sheikh Sidi kassem, who came to the region from the province of Tizi Ouzou. This was the first time that the hammam was built. During the French occupation, religious activity in the corner was stopped and the function of the hammam was limited to bathing only. After independence, no significant modifications were made except for the restoration of the building's roof and the division of the hammam from the inside into seven rooms (five for men and two for women). The maximum room capacity is seven people. An outdoor swimming pool was also built, and there is a hot water pool next to the hammam, which is frequented by young people, especially in the winter, in addition to a parking lot next to the hammam. Most of the visitors to the hammam are from neighboring municipalities in addition to some municipalities of other province such as Constantine, Batna and Setif. We also recorded visitors from outside Algeria, especially from France, and the

majority of them are citizens of the municipality. The hammam is currently managed by the heirs of Sidi Kassem, and the ownership of the land is considered a waqf for the corners of Sheikh Sidi Kassem

Figure 4. Hammam sisi kassem

Figure 5. pool next to the hammam

Figure 6. Parking

Figure 7. Heated swimming pool

Source: authors

4.3 The SWOT analysis of the tourism in Hammam sisi kassem

In the tourism sector, several authors have used the SWOT analysis to understand better the challenges the tourism sector faces at different levels (Nezha et al., 2021). The SWOT analysis of this research was based on two major categories (Mondal, 2017). a. Analysis internal factors: Analyze relevant strengths and weaknesses presented by internal environment. Strengths and weaknesses constituted factors within the system that enable and hinder the organization from achieving its goal, respectively. b. Analysis external factors: Analyze relevant opportunities and threats presented by external environment. Opportunities and threats were considered as exogenous factors that facilitate and limit the system in attaining its goals, respectively

Table 1. Swot analysis

Strengths (+)	Weaknesses (-)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The various medicinal properties and health advantages of thermal waters - Hammam sisi kacem is a place of history and gathering, besides being a hammam. -The hot springs are surrounded by stunning natural landscape -Local customs and cultural legacy; religious sites to be visited -The expense of bathing is low -Rich in natural resources, grouz Dam, grouz mountains and forests -The local cuisine offers traditional meals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - inadequate area marketing and promotion - Lack of information about curative benefits of the thermal waters - Lack of management of medical and curative activity - Absence of certain tourism amenities - pollution and degradation of water quality - Lack of touristic guide to the natural and cultural attractions of the area surrounding thermal springs - Absence of a plan to develop thermal tourism - The problem of land ownership - The lack of an accurate study of the source of water and the available quantity
Opportunities (+)	Threats (-)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Administrative and geographical location For the municipality of Oued athmania - The possibility of developing medical and health tourism - Transforming the area into a touristic destination - Stimulating other types of tourism, such as mountain tourism - Positive impact in the local economy - Availability of the security factor in the region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of government funds for scientific research in areas with touristic potential - Minimal services that do not meet the demands of some customers, especially the upper class - Absence of a strategy by the state to develop thermal tourism - The inability of investors (private or state) to invest in termale tourism due to land ownership problems (family ownership) or the lack of documents - The weight of procedures for developing thermal tourism in the region in terms of laws or investment

5. Result and discussion

5.1 context

All the previous studies conducted on the tourism industry in Algeria have shed light on the country's diverse natural resources and its rich cultural and artistic heritage. This diversity enables the proper utilization of a wide range of tourism activities, including the thermal tourism sector. Despite the availability of natural, economic, and human resources, the Algerian government has not shied away from expressing worry over this situation. because the new major challenge for tourism as a social and economic activity is how tourism stakeholders interact and how this interaction can be beneficial in improving the tourist destination, although inter-organizational governance is essential for tourism policymaking, destination planning and management, destination marketing, integration of distribution channels, and sustainability attention should firstly be paid to the governance environment before the identification of specific models. The environment is defined here as the physical and social factors that should be taken into consideration directly during the decision-making process (Song et al., 2013). Regarding the Sidi Kassem hammam, it arose in several historical, economic, political and legislative contexts that later influenced the activity of this hammam.

Algeria currently is developing an overall strategy. The approach is reflected in the development of the Master Plan for Tourism Development 2030 (SDAT). A long-term policy. The SDAT derives its essence and its coherence from the National Land Use Plan. Operationally broken down into concrete actions on the ground (in progress). In this context, the SDAT is an instrument that reflects the State's desire to exploit the country's natural, cultural and historical potential and to put it at the (meftah et al., 2022). a plan for developing thermal tourism was drawn up at the national level within the framework of the provisions of Executive Decree 69-07, dated February 19, 2007, amended and supplemented by Executive Decree 19-150, dated April 29, 2019. The SDAT 2030 establishes the parameters of a tourist project for the various stakeholders involved with the goal of promoting the industry and guaranteeing development regardless of oil income. In order to put the SDAT's recommendations into practice, This led to the creation of a development plan for this tourism sector's short-, medium-, and long-term objectives by prioritizing goals, axes, and operations based on their level of importance. The draft strategic plan is based on developing strategic scenarios for the regional division for the short term (2016-2020), the medium term (2021-2025), and the long term (2026-2030). By utilizing the capabilities at hand and removing restrictions on this activity in order to upgrade this sector and help contribute to the diversification of the economy, thermal tourism is growing and developing in Algeria. Although (SDAT) was established in order to develop thermal tourism in Algeria, but this program not clarify the mechanisms and applied texts, nor even the institutions charged with developing thermal tourism, with the exception of the administrative file for obtaining a license to exploit thermal waters for private sector investors, and the actors were not identified with a clear goal. The division of duties and roles of each actor in participating in the development of thermal tourism, local groups and civil society did not specify the specificities of the local culture of the regions, customs and traditions.

Most of the hammams arose in different historical contexts. As for the Sidi Kassem hammam, it is considered a legacy from the era of the Roman presence in the region. As regarding the thermal springs available currently has been made up starting from the heritage left respectively by the Romans and the French. During the Roman period, several springs of water were discovered and the sites, of which have been arranged and used because of the benefits of their warm waters (Nedjar and Chergui, 2018). For the Arabian society, thermal therapy is both religious and medical, marriage preparation is traditionally performed at the Hammam (traditional baths). Indeed, this is where wedding rituals are celebrated according to customs and traditions, It is believed that the Hammam is surrounded and inhabited by the Sollah or the Salihine, commonly called in the society's cultural fabric - the good spirits of places and waters. The infertile women pray intercession and pledge (fertas et al., 2022) .currently Ownership of the land is an endowment for the family that established the hammam for religious purposes, Prayer and teaching the Qur'an (zawiya of Sidi Kassem), and Although endowment properties are a fertile field for investing in and developing them and making them an important source in serving the community to achieve social solidarity, and also Converting it into a source of income for a large group of families, and to serve the country's economy (Slimane, 2024). However, the state has set impossible conditions for investment in endowment properties, including the multiplicity of bodies managing endowment properties, most of which are advisory. The problem of the guarantees provided by the investor in order to

preserve endowment properties has also been raised, which Algerian law considers part of Algeria's historical identity.

The delay in the legal texts that regulate tourism activity as a whole, including thermal tourism, result of circumstances (political, economic and security), The black decade and maybe the influence of oil in the Algerian economy have contributed to this decrease (Boulhila et al, 2022) especially in the nineties, UNCTAD (2013) reports that adverse events such as natural disasters, epidemics, political unrest, and terrorism can affect tourism demand. Tourists are sensitive to the political and/or economic image of the host country. The existing literature on the terrorism-tourism nexus is also in broad consensus on the detrimental role of terrorist attacks on tourism-related activity (Topcu et al., 2023). In Algeria This situation resulted led to the expansion of the activity of several sectors without government control. Consequently, this activity imposed unexpected challenges for the government, and thermal tourism in the study area became an element of the system. Where The context of this external system creates opportunities and constraints from the influences of the implementation collaborative governance (Slamet Santoso & Djumiarti, 2020)

5.2 role of government

Were the governments still play important roles because they are often the principal actors in political processes, and they often remain responsible for providing incentives and imposing requirements on actors in promoting objectives around common goals (Penny Wan & Bramwell ,2015). And Governments influence the tourism sector in a variety of roles and capacities: border security, regulation of aviation markets; management of tourist attractions such as national parks and beaches; and through funding infrastructure such as roads and convention centers (Scott et al., 2015). In this framework, the government's directive functions, under current conditions, are particularly relevant in coordinating efforts to help ensure that the dynamic of permanent growth that tourism has achieved to date is economically, socially and environmentally sustainable so as to increase its contribution to development (Durán, 2013). Examples of vital things that must be regulated by the government are spatial planning that prioritizes the needs of the community and guarantees the preservation of sacred areas and conservation areas (Gede Oka Wisnumurti et al., 2020). By completing a tourism plan that highlights the uniqueness of Hammam Sidi Kassem from tourism, religious, historical and cultural perspective, Among the works that the government must do is to upgrade and improve the infrastructure, such as lighting, preparing the place by removing the weeds on the edges of the valley, Parking lot preparation, and building a small hotel to accommodate the number of people visiting the bathroom. Among these collaborative actions, it is the ones focused on environmental quality and protection that are crucial for the development of environmentally sustainable tourism (Erkus, & Eraydin, 2010). Implementing an eco-tax that can leave in public hands part of the income generated by tourism, with the objective of achieving maximum social benefit. This tax consists of the use of a group of regulations and taxes to achieve certain level of environmental quality (Barandiarán et al., 2019). It can also Promoting thermal tourism and ecotourism together Hammamat Sidi Kacem is located at the foot of the mountain. These mountains are covered with dense forests. You can also benefit from the grouz Dam for fishing. This necessitated directing attention to the need to organize and control the marketing and promotion of these activities in order to reach the desired goals in the time and level required (Noori & Al-Rawi, 2023). Where Currently, ecotourism is positioned as one of the promising types of nature-oriented tourism, which is developing dynamically (Osipchuk et al., 2022). Organize, coordinate and government Cooperation among government actors where increased participation of multiple actors can result in difficult situations, where steering becomes an issue (Bramwell & Lane, 2011). This is especially relevant in the context of tourism governance that addresses processes and structures (Bichler, 2021). In the field of interorganizational theory, Gray suggests that collaboration occurs when the problem is complex and a single organization cannot solve it on its own. It is a process in which those parties with a stake in the problem actively seek a mutually determined solution (Bramwellb & Sharman, 1999). As we noticed in this studied example where The multiplicity of stakeholders has become an obstacle to the development of thermal tourism in the area, such as the Ministry of Religious Affairs and Endowments, the Ministry of Tourism, the State Property Directorate, and many others. The government must provide safety and security creating conditions for tourists to feel secure and safe from harm before and during a trip is critical to the success of many destinations (Agarwal et al., 2021). As is known, Algeria suffered from insecurity and instability in the nineties, which made it an undesirable tourist destination, especially for foreign tourists.

5.3 role of private sector

Due to increasingly complicated social and political circumstances like rising community aspirations for democracy, deregulation and marketization, economic recession, globalization, global calls for sustainable development, and crises and disasters, governments are no longer able to steer alone (penny wan et al., 2022). A suitable balance between public and private sector is vital in ensuring optimal tourism outcomes for destination areas. The implication is that tourism policy and planning now occur by incorporating state and non-state organizations. Rather, an increase in partnerships between governments and businesses is created through which tourism flourish or stagnate and decline (Kubickova & Campbell, 2018). The tourism sector in Algeria was not a priority for investment until recently, which led to the delay of laws related to its promotion. Therefore, we find among the imbalances that the tourism sector in Algeria suffers from the exclusion of the private sector from investment in the field of tourism, except for some limited activities such as hotel services. To address this deficiency, new mechanisms were established to involve the private sector in promoting tourism in all its forms. This is what was stated in the guiding plan for tourism development, Horizons 2025, which calls for working with the public-private partnership plan, as the latter seeks to create links between the various actors in the tourism process, whether public or private, in order to confront foreign competition and achieve a qualitative tourism product, and make the Algerian facade more attractive and competitive, to reach a level of tourism maturity that elevates Algeria to the ranks of the most preferred tourist countries. The same plan also referred to the methods of the state's support for the private sector, including supporting investors and project owners by helping them in decision-making, in financing equipment and assessing risks, easing bank loan procedures, extending the loan period, training assistance, and comprehensive encouragement of quality. However, despite these measures the private sector's contribution to the promotion of hammam Sidi Kassem is distinguished by a unique feature that distinguishes it from the rest of the hammams in the province of mila, which can be exploited in developing thermal tourism, including reviving the historical dimension of the region and the religious heritage represented in the role of the corner in religious education, which was considered the main role of the region, establishing a partnership with the government sector where the government is responsible for restoring the bath and the mosque together and the private sector is responsible for managing this initiative, which involves several actors, including the government represented by the ministry of tourism with financial support and the ministry of endowments and religious affairs through financial and human support, the province of mila and the local authority of the municipality of oued athmania by providing services and infrastructure. In order to achieve this partnership, the private sector must build hotels and manage their affairs, In exchange, the government may reduce or eliminate taxes for a specific period. Additionally, consultations will be conducted to gather suggestions and insights for the development of thermal tourism in the region. Advertising efforts will be carried out via current social media platforms, and training programs will be established to prepare skilled workers for managing thermal tourism operations.

5.4 role of local authority

Local authority in Algeria are a geographical expression defined regionally, a population cluster defined numerically and a mini administrative unit of the state, and in order to best embody the objectives of decentralization, they have been entrusted with a set of powers that take into account the extension and expansion of central tasks at the local level and the increasing volume of local public needs of the region. Local authority in Algeria are considered effective institutions and directly responsible for implementing economic, social and local development programs. They represent one of the most important basic institutions of the Algerian state, given the role they are distinguished by as an administrative body that has been entrusted with many and varied tasks. In this context, Algerian legislation has granted broad powers to local authority in order to perform well and attract more local or foreign investments, including the tasks of promoting local tourism. Article 122 of the municipal law issued in 2011 states that the municipality must take every measure aimed at expanding its tourism capabilities and encouraging the operators concerned with exploiting them. However, anyone who follows the reality of thermal tourism in the study area realizes the clear defect in the performance of the municipality's tasks. The Local authority inability to intervene to promote thermal tourism has legal and economic justifications the most important: The problem of real estate ownership of a hammam Sidi Kacem, the waqf lands are not legally part of the municipality's property. The municipality's limited financial resources,

most of the projects are directed towards infrastructure, the tourism sector has not received its sufficient share of the municipality's budget. The municipality cannot intervene in the development of the thermal spring or the valley because they are state property and the municipality cannot impose taxes on the bath because the bath is not registered in the directorate of commercial activities, nor can it apply any tax of any kind without consulting the directorate of taxes, tourism and endowments.

On this basis, the municipality's intervention in the study area is restricted by several laws and linked to several actors, and this is what was observed in the field from the deterioration and delay of all the projects programmed for the Sidi kassem bath in order to upgrade it and restore its reputation.

Most of the literature that has addressed the role of local authorities in improving tourist destinations states that local authorities have an important role in the success of the local tourism industry, and in preserving resources. As They also have a role in to promote the social, economic, environmental and cultural well-being of their communities and their involvement in tourism must be related to that (Aser & elazique, 2011) where local authorities are better placed than other institutions operating at higher levels of government to balance national and local interests and to integrate urban and rural initiatives with national development (Nunkoo, 2015). The multiplicity of local government roles is also recognised by other authors, which can be conceptualised broadly under the binary of enablement (e.g. facilitation) and management (e.g. regulation). (Roxas et al., 2020). Regarding Hammam Sidi Kassem, the role of local authorities can be summarized as:

Facilitate participatory planning and monitoring to promote community empowerment

Improving the image of the thermal tourist destination

Coordination between actors at all levels as the representative of the state over the local on the one hand and those closest to the private sector and the local community on the other hand.

Influence the social representations of tourism for local communities how these communities can benefit from its activities.

Developing an action program that links social and environmental issues

Practice and promote responsible advertising

Developing infrastructure and improving services

5.5 High synergy of governments, private sector and Local authority in management of tourism thermal

By analyzing this model (hammam sidi kassem), the key factors which influence the governance performance are:

Power asymmetry and divergent interests as Public sector and private sector

Contextual factors such as history, culture, legislation, and politics.

The fragmented nature of the tourism industry

Lack of integration between the government, the private sector and local authority

Limited organizational capabilities for all actors.

Difficulty to combine the efforts of actors for effective marketing of the tourist destination

Centralization of decision making for local governments that remain tied to the government

Through these factors, three basic dimensions were identified in order to adopt the model shown in Figure No. (08). Include analysis on actors, their roles and relationships. Cooperation and coordination between all these stakeholders are foundations to local development. All of these stakeholders share the resources in destination and develop various formal and informal networks (Zhang & Zhu 2014). The development of tourism thermal requires a solid partnership between the three main elements, the government, the private sector, and local authority, Good governance can be achieved if all actors work together and are able to share power, expertise and resources

Figure 8. Development tourism thermal hammam sidi kassem

Fuente: own elaboration

6 Conclusions

Conditions related to the Sidi Kassem hammam and the Grouz thermal spring, both present and past, are known to the government, the private sector, and the local authorities. These conditions will influence the monitoring and continuation of cooperation among the three parties.

Thermal Tourism governance in the study area implies complex and comprehensive coordination that can influence destination competitiveness. If the initiative takes place, we will notice the reproduction of the same fragmented nature in the tourism sector. The success of CG relies on whether the members of a collaborative network are able to develop new processes that will lead to new ways of working, new structural arrangements and integration of the members into a new whole, which will lead to the accomplishment of innovative solutions (Bichler & Löscher, 2019). Applying collaborative governance in thermal tourism management in this example involves several challenges internal and external. Taking into account that collaborative governance links multiple stakeholders through shared spaces that enhance participation and consensus in decision-making, on this basis, these shared spaces can activate the role of collaborative governance through holding a coordination meeting that brings together all actors concerned with the development of thermal tourism in the study area in order to build a cooperative approach and identify the basic components that could enter into a concept of governance applicable to thermal tourism, build consensus and define a collective action map, match public needs and tourism objectives according to a common strategic vision, diagnose the most important obstacles and difficulties facing the development of the thermal tourism sector by employing the latest data, ensure real stakeholder participation in local tourism development by directly involving stakeholders in the decision-making process, expand the scope of participation to include local associations, research centers, travel agencies, etc. ensure transparency in management, building trust between the actors and avoiding conflicts of the past,

communicate until positive indicators of cooperative governance emerge, Commitment to the collaborative process in managing local thermal tourism

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